

Melting characteristics of a series of polyester resin derived from ϵ -caprolactone and different glycols

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Abstract : α,ω -Dihydroxy terminated polyester resins in the form of macroglycols of molecular weight, on the order of $\sim 2 \times 10^3$, were synthesized by polymerization of ϵ -caprolactone in the presence of different glycol initiating additives. The macroglycols were characterized by physico-chemical techniques. The hydroxyl groups of such macroglycols were present as terminals while etheral ($-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$) and non-etheral ($-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$) linkages, connecting the polyester segments, occupied the central part of the macroglycol molecule. The WAXD pattern indicated the presence of crystal structure in the macroglycols. The presence of non-etheral and etheral group played important role to influence the melting point of macroglycols. The enthalpy of melting of the macroglycols was found to remain in the range of 36 J/g to 111 J/g.

Keywords : Polyester resin, glycol, ϵ -caprolactone, melting point.

Introduction

For the development of a chemical sensor, the general technological approach is basically the application of a sorbent thin film over a suitable electronic device for the detection of specific analyte. These sorbent materials will strongly and selectively sorb the vapour of interest with the concomitant reduction in frequency of oscillating piezoelectric device, where the interface selectively interact with the analyte to transform the desired chemical parameter into a signal^{1,2}.

The search for an interfacial material endowed with specificity, sensitivity, stability and reversibility for sensing of analytes is of prime importance for the development of efficient sensors. The earliest interface materials were some kind of inorganic salts and complexes of transition metals. But of late because of the tailorability in polymers, they are being explored for this purpose¹. In fact, certain kind of polymer coating sorbent placed at the interface between the transducer and the target can act as chemical sensor.

Polymers of low T_g below ambient temperature are

preferred as sorbent coating materials for sensor devices because of their easy response due to the rapid diffusion of organic vapours through the polymer. Often polyester family of resins is potential sorbent coating material useful for detection of organophosphorous compounds using surface acoustic wave (SAW) sensors^{2,3}. A typical example of such organophosphorous compounds is dimethyl methylphosphonate (DMMP) – a nerve stimulating agent. It is reported that the response of detector is better when polyesters were used as coating material in preference to inorganic materials¹. For example, polyethylene maleate (PEM) based coating materials are sometimes considered suitable material for this purpose. Structure of polyester based material plays an important role in influencing selectivity and sensitivity towards organo-compounds, particularly organophosphorous compounds. It is also reported that by increasing chain length in glycol components, the response and selectivity of piezoelectric quartz crystal can be improved.

With this background information, in the present preliminary work, this paper reports the synthesis, characterization of a family of low melting hydroxyl terminated

polyester resins bearing a central block having variable non-etheral and etheral moieties, intended to reducing the T_g below ambient temperature with a molecular weight in the range of 2000 which may be useful in similar applications mentioned above.

Macroglycols are also popularly known as polyester polyols in the industry, so the term is used interchangeably here. Polyester polyols, a class of macroglycols having functionality (f) generally between 2 and 3 are often used as the important precursor constituent material for various syntheses of specialty block copolymers with low T_g ^{4,5}. Besides the classical polycondensation reaction of dicarboxylic acids and glycols⁶, the alternative method of synthesis of aliphatic polyester polyol can be achieved through the ring opening polymerization of lactone⁷ as per the following reaction scheme :

Thus the ring opening polymerization of lactones, $(\text{CH}_2)_m\text{CO}_2$ in the presence of a suitable reacting initiator additive, say diol (OH-R-OH) may be a convenient method of synthesis of main chain polyesters possessing an aliphatic structure^{4,7}. This process is of importance because it is rather difficult to obtain some of these polyols with desired hydroxyl terminated chemical structure by classical methods of polyesterification. More importantly, ring-opening polymerization technique provides some advantages^{4,6,7}. One of the advantages, for example, is that there is no liberation of byproducts like water molecule in the ring opening polymerization scheme (eq. 1); therefore, it should be particularly suitable for the synthesis of void-free polyurethane based coated sorbent material because it avoids the chance of liberation of CO_2 due to the absence of reaction between water molecule and the diisocyanates^{4,8} in the reaction system. The absence of water as byproduct may be particularly suitable in providing more consistent and reliable response during the course of experiments. In this article, synthesis of a class of polyester polyols of different chemical structures and their melting point characterization are discussed.

Experimental

Materials : Ethylene glycol (EG); diethylene glycol (DEG); 1,4-butane diol, 1,5-pentane diol; 1,6-hexane diol; polyethylene glycols (PEGs) of different molecular weights such as PEG-200, PEG-400, PEG-600 (SD fine chemicals); ϵ -caprolactone (Aldrich) all were dried under vacuum before use.

Instruments : IR : Perkin-Elmer IR was used to obtain the spectra.

NMR : Jeol FX 90Q FT NMR was used to characterize the polyols with reference to the internal reference, $\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_4(\text{TMS})$ with δ at 0 for TMS.

Wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) : The WAXD patterns were obtained with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation from Rich Seifert X-ray generator.

Du Pont DSC instrument with 910 module was used to determine the melting transition and enthalpy (ΔH , J/g). An oxygen free nitrogen stream of 40 cc/min was maintained through the cell during the measurements. The scan was performed at a rate of 2° K/min.

Synthesis : Polyester polyols having molecular weights on the order of $\sim 2 \times 10^3$ were synthesized by polymerization of ϵ -caprolactone in the presence of different glycol reacting initiator additives like $\text{HO}(\text{CH}_2)_x\text{OH}$ and $\text{HO}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_y\text{OH}$, where $x = 2, 4, 5, 6$ i.e. homolog of ethylene glycol and $y = 2, 4, 8, 12$ i.e. homologs of diethylene ether glycol. The reactions were carried out in an environment of dry argon at 215 °C in the presence of desired quantities of glycols.

The polymerization was carried out in a two-necked reaction vessel equipped with the argon gas inlet. Predetermined quantities of ϵ -caprolactone and diols were charged into the reaction vessel at 215 ± 1 °C with an arrangement of high-speed stirrer. The polymerization time was found to be 24 h by trial and error method. The polyols were purified by reprecipitation from the mixture of chloroform and n-hexane solvents under centrifugation at a speed of 3.5×10^4 rpm for a period of 6 h.

The white wax-like polyols were isolated and dried under vacuum at 65 °C for 22 h.

Average molecular weight (M_n) : The (M_n) of the polyols was evaluated from the determination of Hydroxyl Number as defined by the ASTM E-222-73.

Results and discussion

The polyester polyol or macroglycol so synthesized are soluble in organic solvents like acetone, methylethyl ketone, acetonitrile, etc. Therefore, coating over the detector can easily be done using the above commonly available solvents. The properties of the polyester polyols are shown in Table 1. IR, NMR were used to characterize

the synthesized polyester polyols. The IR spectrum of one of the macroglycols (ϵ -P200) typically derived from ϵ -caprolactone and polyethylene glycol of molecular weight (PEG-200) is shown in Fig. 1. The ester groups of the polyester polyols were absorbed as doublet in the IR region at 1719 and 1733 cm^{-1} due to C=O and C-O stretching. The distinct absorption in the range of 3423 to 3354 cm^{-1} indicated O-H stretching with varying extent of hydrogen bonding in the polyester polyol. The presence of alkane groups ($-\text{CH}_2-$)_n was revealed from the absorption in the ranges of 737 to 740 cm^{-1} along with 711 to 736 cm^{-1} and 2842 to 2926 cm^{-1} respectively which correspond to different kinds of methylene groups such as one in the central position of the polyol molecule and other near the hydroxyl groups^{9,10}. Polyols with more than four consecutive methylene groups present in the open chain which are responsible for rocking and wagging of the $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups were clearly visible in the band region near around 720 cm^{-1} ^{9,10} in all the synthesized macroglycols. All the other macroglycols showed the same kind of IR absorption pattern.

In the ¹H NMR spectra each of the polyols showed absorption near 3.66 ppm and 2 ppm in the form of triplets corresponding to different methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) groups attached to the $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{COO}$ groups respectively. Between these two triplets one more smaller triplet was observed which was due to the methylene groups derived from reacting initiator glycol additives. The broadened triplets near 1.2 ppm correspond to the three central

Table 1. Melting points and molecular weights of the polyester polyols

Polyester polyols or macroglycols ^a	Central moiety of the polyol	Melting point (°C)		M_n
		Capillary	DSC	
ϵ -EG	$-(\text{CH}_2)_2-$	52	57.66	2086
ϵ -1,4-But	$-(\text{CH}_2)_4-$	51	56.57	2185
ϵ -1,5-Pent	$-(\text{CH}_2)_5-$	48	56.23	2168
ϵ -1,6-Hex	$-(\text{CH}_2)_6-$	49	56.60	2290
ϵ -DEG	$-(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_2-$	45	53.94	2172
ϵ -P200	$-(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_4-$	43	53.55	2158
ϵ -P400	$-(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_8-$	41	50.79	2010
ϵ -P600	$-(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_{12}-$	40	47.35	2080

*Marking ϵ stands for polyols derived from ϵ -caprolactone and the subsequent letters represent the reaction initiators used for the synthesis of macroglycol, i.e. ϵ -EG stands for macroglycol prepared from ϵ -caprolactone and ethylene glycol. And ϵ -P400 represents macroglycol prepared from ϵ -caprolactone and PEG of molecular weight 400 etc.

Fig. 1. Infrared spectral profile of a typical poly (ϵ -caprolactone) glycol, ϵ -P200.

methylene groups of the lactone part was observed. Fig. 2 is a typical ^1H NMR spectrum of a representative polyol such as ϵ -P200, where ϵ -P200 represents macroglycol synthesized from ϵ -caprolactone and PEG-200.

Fig. 2. ^1H NMR spectral profile of a typical poly (ϵ -caprolactone) glycol, ϵ -P200.

The hydroxyl groups (-OH) were present as terminals at the chain ends while ethereal or nonethereal linkages, derived from initiator component, occupied the central part of these polyester polyol chains. Ethereal linkages (- CH_2O -) were formed in the polyester polyol when the lactone ring was opened by the initiating reactants like diethylene glycol (DEG) or polyethylene glycols (PEGs) such as PEG-200, PEG-400, PEG-600. On the other hand, nonethereal methylene linkages (- CH_2 -) were formed at the center of the polyol chain when 1,2-ethane diol (EG), 1,4-butane diol, 1,5-pentane diol or 1,6-hexane diol was used as initiating additives in the reacting system.

The wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) pattern in the region of 21 to 25° (Fig. 3) indicated that all such polyols were largely crystalline. The melting points (m.p.) of the polyols as determined by the usual classical capillary method showed interesting results. Such melting point was also evaluated by DSC method to corroborate the observation of melting point value by the capillary method. Interestingly, in both methods the trend of melting patterns was found to be same (Table 1). It may be noted that although the melting point (m.p.) data vary considerably with the method of measurement but the trend of

such data remained the same. This difference in melting point due to the change in the method of measurement is not unexpected as it may depend upon the heating rate applied during the measurement^{8,11} under experiment. It

Fig. 3. XRD profile of a typical poly (ϵ -caprolactone) glycol, ϵ -P200.

is seen from the Table 1 that with the gradual change in the chemical structures, the m.p. of the polyols changed - even though small (e.g. $\Delta T_{m,DSC} = 1^\circ$) but it appears it has a tendency to showing the *odd-even* fluctuation of m.p. in tune with the length of the methylene groups in the central moiety of the polyols (Table 1, upper part). Such type of melting behavior was generally observed in the case of nylon family of polymer system, derived from aliphatic carboxylic acids having varying methylene chain lengths^{8,12}. DSC evaluation indicated the melting points and heat of fusion (ΔH_f) of the polyester polyols remained in the range of 47.35 to 57.66 °C and 36.12 to 111.0 J/g for the ethereal and non-ethereal based polyols respectively. Thus, the central moiety played an important and specific role to control the m.p. of the polyester polyols. The polyester polyols with ethereal central moiety showed both melting point and ΔH_f lower than those of their non-ethereal counterparts. When the central part contains ether group, then the melting point decreases with the increase in the number of ether moiety (-O-) in the polyester polyol. Ether group (-O-) is known for its rotational freedom and because of the facile rotational freedom of the ether group in the macroglycols, there is decrease in melting point with increase in ether group in the chain.

It is worthwhile to mention here that the molecular weight (M_n) of the polyester polyols so synthesized in the present work remained in the range around 2000 which are reportedly used in many occasions as sorbent material for target analytes. Therefore, such reactions allow almost regular control of molecular weight to about 2000 endowed with bifunctional ($f = 2$) hydroxyl reactive groups. And this range of molecular weights is desirable to develop certain kind of block copolymers^{1,2}. Thus,

such reaction approach is considered as an ideal technique for certain critical areas of product development, say, in the development of sorbent coating material for the analytes. Therefore, the work is pragmatically utile in the development of a family of α,ω -dihydroxy terminated polyester polymers for possible application as sorbent material for some target analytes.

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